

Performance analysis of smart optimization antenna for wireless networks

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 27, 2022

Revised Mar 9, 2023

Accepted Mar 28, 2023

Keywords:

Communication

Optimization

Parameters

Smart antenna

Wireless networks

ABSTRACT

Antenna design has significantly advanced as a result of the widespread need for wireless communications and data substitution through wireless devices. The research article's goal is to provide a conceptual framework, difficulties, and opportunities for a source as well as a general overview of the antenna used in wireless communications applications. In this proposed research, we will go over a variety of topics related to mobile communication and fifth generation (5G) technologies, including its pros and benefits. A thorough comparison between the expected properties of the antennas and each generation, from 1st generation (1G) to 5G, is also included. This article also provides an overview of the investigated 5G technologies and various antenna designs.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The diversity of wireless networks today is growing as a result of considerable advancements in radio access technologies. usage of mobile devices with multimedia capabilities, high-definition movies, various applications and software, elite gaming, augmented reality and virtual reality. Over the next years, this will cause a noticeable increase in user data traffic. To handle this, cutting-edge methods, fresh services, and brand-new instruments must be created for the upcoming fifth generation (5G) offerings. Many nations presented recommendations during the world radio congress (WRC 15) conference regarding the frequency bands that might be used for impending 5G connectivity. The 5G systems, which can support high data rate services, are now being defined, designed, and developed by businesses and academic organizations. 2018 saw the allocation of 5G new radio (NR) bands in the sub-6 short for gigahertz (GHz) spectrum for impending mobile broadband services, but certain bands above 6 GHz are also encouraged to be investigated and tested for 5G communication. Multi-element antenna systems are necessary given the advancements achieved in wireless technology. In a scattering environment, a multiple input and multiple output (MIMO) system uses many antennas at each location to offer several uncorrelated channels between the transmitter and receiver. These MIMO antenna devices need to be small and provide a range of functions. Therefore, what is required at this time is a discrete framework that generates tiny gadgets and lovely designs [1]–[5].

Through the internet, a substantial heterogeneous network of gadgets of various sorts will be linked together, necessitating a communication network that can accommodate so many gadgets. The internet of things (IoT) is a recent technology that connects and facilitates communication between many sensors, appliances, and other devices. The mutual coupling is somewhat over permissible limits in the majority of MIMO systems. Several methods, including as the use of slots on the ground plane, T-shaped slot impedance transformers, modified ground structures, use of metamaterial (MTM) structures, use of neutralization line structures, and others, have been suggested to enhance these MIMO properties. Most modern smartphones have two MIMO antenna components for fourth generation/fourth generation long-term evolution (4G/4G LTE) and wireless local area network (WLAN) services. There will be a greater need for antenna components in the future when wireless devices can handle much larger data rates.

Recent studies have shown two or four-component MIMO antenna designs for smartphones that support 5G frequency ranges. The four element MIMO planar inverted-F antenna (PIFA) antenna system for mobile devices is the subject of the research discussed in this article. A complementary MTM unit cell is used on the ground plane to increase isolation by reducing mutual coupling between the components, which is one of the novel aspects of the proposed antenna. Theory of characteristic mode (TCM) is systematically used to design the antenna structure. According to our knowledge, this is the first antenna that can operate in both the unlicensed 17 GHz spectrum for IoT applications and the 4G/5G communication frequencies. To accomplish multi-band behavior and exceptional radiation properties, a compact L-shaped antenna element with edge feeding is created. The article's subsequent parts, which are broken up into subheadings, provide a short overview of TCM and describe how it may be used to identify significant modes in radiating components, ground planes, and the whole PIFA geometry. A single element antenna and a four-element MIMO system make up the development of the suggested antenna design [6]–[10].

One of the plate's corners was cut off, creating an L-shaped feature, to enhance the plate's performance below 6 GHz shows the CMA outcomes for the altered rectangular plate with a L-shape. Researchers from across the world are creating cellular hardware ecosystems for backward compatibility since it can be shown that the modes are rather comparable to what we saw in the case of rectangular plates. Microwave engineers have created components that are compatible with the established protocols in response to the surge in smartphone use. LTE a new technology, will be available in portable devices for voice and data applications. Three low-frequency bands are frequently used: LTE2300/Class 40 band (2,300–2,400 MHz), LTE2500/Class 7 band, and LTE700 (698–787 MHz). (2,500–2,690 MHz). MIMO, or multiple input, multiple output, is one of the best methods for achieving high data rates. The LTE antenna's vast physical size imposes a design restriction that makes it difficult to integrate into mobile terminals. Future transceivers will need to support both futureWave 5G and 4G LTE antennas. For the construction of 5G antennas, frequencies for mmWave 5G are anticipated to be in the 28 GHz range. It might be difficult to provide a variety of orthogonal designs with a small physical footprint. To guarantee the backward compatibility of future phones, the issue of 4G LTE and mmWave 5G MIMO antennas on the same module has to be addressed. In order to accommodate the available antennas into the limited space within the phone, their footprint will need to be reduced. It is difficult to cohabit mmWave 5G antennas with 4G LTE antennas on the same module. Even though the combined effective radiating volume of the 4G LTE and mmWave 5G antennas is electrically enormous, the designs have demonstrated their co-design. For several situations where the surface is not flat, conformal antennas have been widely investigated. (Either one curve or two curves). A small design is necessary due to limited space. The schematics show the conformal mobile antennas in both portrait and landscape orientations.

2. SMART ANTENNA

In this study, the combined 4G LTE/mmWave 5G antenna design is shown within the limitations of a common smartphone. Systems for 4G LTE systems and mmWave 5G MIMO antennas were created independently and then combined with the proper amount of isolation. MmWave 5G MIMO antenna technology covers the 28 GHz mmWave range, while 4GMIMO antenna technology covers the class 7 LTE spectrum. An investigation is made into 4G LTE MIMO antenna design. Using computer simulation technology (CST) Microwave Studio, 4G LTE antennas are simulated. The 4G MIMO antenna system uses the Rogers 5870 substrate, which has a dielectric constant (ϵ_r) of 2.33 and a loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) of 0.0012. A substrate with a low dielectric constant is used to reduce surface wave modes. The substrate's 10 mil thickness makes it simpler to achieve compliance. The high loss tangent of flexible surfaces like polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polycarbonate will cause further gain degradation. Although the 5mil substrate needs more scaffolding than the substrate advised for conformal designs, it is more flexible. Modelling and evaluation were done on the observed input reflection co-efficient (S11) for the 4G LTE conformal and planar antennas. Using an Agilent PNA E8364C vector network analyzer, the data were quantified.

Covering the class 7 LTE frequency is the conformal 4G LTE antenna. The suggested conformal 4G LTE antenna's fractional bandwidth is around 5.8%, which is higher than that of comparable designs. Its measured impedance bandwidth ranges from 2.5 to 2.65 GHz. When changing from a planar to a conformal shape, the conformal micro antenna's decreased impedance bandwidth is shown. This is brought on by a discontinuity in the antenna that develops after a 90-degree bend. The observed mismatch between the measured and simulated data might be the result of manufacturing tolerances. The substrate's differential dielectric constant may also be to blame for the frequency shift. The anechoic chamber's inadequate oblique incidence absorptivity is to blame for the discrepancies between the simulated and measured findings. The fact that the cross-polarization radiation patterns in both planes are reported to be 25 dB smaller than the co-polarization radiation patterns [11]–[15] suggests that the antenna is highly linearly polarized. Given the antenna's electrical size, the observed and expected gain ranges of the recommended antennas, which range from 1.6 to 2.2 dBi within the operational band, indicate a reasonable gain yield. Because of the proposed 4G LTE antenna's use of an electrically thin substrate, its predicted radiation efficiency ranges between 75 and 90%. In comparison to other published antennas, the suggested 4G LTE antenna is conformal, electrically compact, and has a comparatively high efficiency and gain yield, as shown by achieved gain and radiation efficiency charts. Differences between simulated and observed results, brought on by connection modelling, substrate inhomogeneity, and manufacturing tolerances, are visible. The proposed 4G LTE MIMO has simulated and measured isolation between two components that is more than 15 dB over the full operating spectrum.

The two-element MIMO antenna that is being suggested has a three-dimensional (3D) gain that operates at 2.6 GHz. The envelope correlation coefficient (ECC) is a crucial performance metric for MIMO antennas. To operate at its best, the antenna module needs as little ECC as feasible. ECC that is suggested for a 4G LTE MIMO antenna. ICT, which includes wireless technologies that use electromagnetic fields like Wi-Fi and mobile telephony (MP), have shown unprecedented growth in recent years. Electromagnetic field (EMF). In a few nations in the late 1980s, the first generation of portable mobile phones was accessible to individual, private users. Due to the tremendous improvements in society penetration rates witnessed by the second generation (2G), third generation (3G), and 4G LTE generations, there are currently more gadgets on the planet than people. The use of Wi-Fi and other wireless data transmission technologies is expanding and becoming increasingly common. The 5G of mobile networks is now being rolled out. It is critical to keep in mind that 5G is an advancement over G1 through G4 technology, not a whole new one.

Future 5G mobile network implementation will provide much higher mobile internet speeds and constantly rising rates of mobile data consumption. This is achievable since more higher frequency bands have been adopted. The communications hub for everything from virtual reality to self-driving cars, the industrial internet, and smart cities is what 5G intends to be. Additionally, 5G is recognized as the foundational technology for the IoT, which allows object-to-object communication. Machine-to-machine (M2M) communication. In addition, it is anticipated that EMF exposure for individuals and the environment would alter. Many of these frequencies, especially those below 1 GHz ultrahigh frequency (UHF), have been or are in use for previous generations of mobile communication. In further phases of technical development, even higher radio frequencies (RF) are also anticipated to be utilized. Wavelengths in the centimeter (3-30 GHz) or millimeter ranges, which are much higher than UHF ranges, are included in the new bands. Millimeter-wave (mmW); 30–300 GHz. Microwave networks and radars have historically utilized these latter bands.

In the mobile device sector, smartphones and other multifunctional gadgets are gaining popularity. These devices are equipped with a variety of mobile contemporary technologies, including Wi-Fi, quick mobile internet 3G and 4G, global positioning system (GPS), global system for mobile communication (GSM), Bluetooth®, and GSM. In an increasingly connected society, internet speeds tend to increase with time, making it feasible to hold real-time video talks using, for example, a connection supplied by a mobile operator. These devices' displays are enlarging as well to improve user experience during high-resolution video talks. Consumers continue to choose smaller-sized technologies despite the expansion of display possibilities. Therefore, it is crucial to minimize the internal components of a smartphone in order to lower its size. Various methods, such as the production of integrated circuits, are used to reduce the size of the circuit. Additionally, printed antennas with a very thin covering are required.

3. OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES METHOD

The need for speedier mobile internet has prompted research and the ongoing development of new technologies like 4G, which can provide data at rates of up to 100 Mbps. The 5G of mobile telecommunications, or 5G, is being studied and developed, although not yet being widely used. It may use electromagnetic spectrum frequency ranges over 25 GHz and operate at extraordinarily high data speeds. The

IoT has raised concerns among mobile technology companies about the potential increase in the number of devices connected at once. As a result, these companies are looking for ways to effectively meet future demand and stress the importance of 5G deployment. This article describes the creation of a microstrip antenna that can support all required smartphone capabilities, including impending 5G technologies, using only one antenna in order to minimize the size of the mobile device. According to the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) standard definition, an antenna is a piece of equipment that may be used for radio wave transmission or reception or as a channel for transferring energy between free space and a waveguide.

Due to its incredibly thin thickness, the team employed a microstrip kind of antenna. The characteristics of this antenna must also be ultra-wideband. Although the microstrip antenna was created in the 1950s, it was not until the 1970s that it was used for space applications, which contributed to its era of prominence. Currently, both commercial and civic applications, especially those involving mobile devices, often employ this kind of antenna. Like smartphones. Most of the microstrip antenna is made up of these three layers: The ground plane is composed of two metallic layers: one over a substrate and the other on top of it. Numerous configurations, also known as design formats, may be used for this third layer. Ground plane. For example, these parameters determine the instrument's operating frequency. The most frequent designs for this kind of antenna are circular and rectangular because they are simple to construct, project (for a limited range of resonance bands), and produce. These structures also have appealing radiation properties and little cross polarization [16]–[20]. Due to their low profile (very thin) construction, these antennas may be used on both flat and crooked surfaces. They are also quite versatile because of how easily they are manufactured and how inexpensively they are made-priced similarly to making printed circuit boards. When placed on solid surfaces, this antenna is also mechanically durable. Not to mention, it is simple to change a variety of antenna characteristics, including resonance frequency, polarization, radiation pattern, and impedance. Any device that consumes 1.5 GHz or more of a spectrum or has a fractional bandwidth larger than 0.25 is classified as an ultra-wideband device by the federal communication commission (FCC), which includes the current project. This kind of antennas may be used for military applications, mobile communications, commercial, medical, and other uses. Wireless standards are being developed in response to the growing need for data transport. The commercial development of the 3G partnership project (3GPP) LTE technology started soon after the first Forzon release in December 2008. In order to enhance capacity, LTE-Advanced, also known as international mobile telecommunications-advanced (IMT-Advanced), was introduced in March 2011. At that time, LTE was officially acknowledged as being a part of the 4G of wireless technology as defined by the International Telecommunication Union. To allow applications like the smart grid, smart cities, and e-health, new traffic kinds and data services are starting to emerge, particularly machine-to-machine interactions. One forecast is that the creation of new applications may result in the connection of 50 billion devices by the year 2020. In the next ten years, cellular networks could need to be able to handle up to 1,000 times as much traffic as they do now (conservative estimates vary from 40% to 70%). Cellular systems beyond 4G and 5G, which provide peak throughputs of several gigabits per second (Gb/s) and cell edge rates in the tens of megabits per second (Mb/s), are being developed in order to handle the difficult challenge of satisfying this demand.

Future networks must be far more energy-efficient than existing networks if they are to be durable and provide more performance than LTE Advanced. The increase in data capacity required for 5G networks to be commercially viable is partly due to mmW beamforming technology. This method operates between 30 and 300 GHz, where the possible bandwidths are far larger than those of present cellular networks. It employs a sizable MIMO system. The additional spectrum made available by the FCC has an 11 GHz bandwidth and is made up of 7 GHz of unlicensed spectrum from 64 to 71 GHz and 3.8 GHz of licensed spectrum from 27.5 to 28.35 GHz and 27.5 to 40 GHz. Furthermore, a mmW signal's comparatively short wavelength, which uses cutting-edge radiofrequency integrated circuit technology, makes it feasible to fabricate an antenna with many (32) tiny components. Therefore, large MIMO systems with extremely high gain, electrically steerable arrays, and adaptive beamforming arrays may one day be used in wireless networks. These systems could also be developed within a chip, terminal, or base station. Even though there are advantages to adopting the mmW band, there are still a number of significant issues that need to be resolved before wireless systems in these bands can be deployed, particularly for the array antenna design. Due to sensitive manufacturing limits and high insertion loss in wave propagation, it is challenging to produce electromagnetic circuit components in the mmW range. Small parameter misalignments on the order of 0.1 mm may cause the properties of the circuit element to alter, which might have unanticipated results.

The shorter wavelength of the mmW signal allows for greater antenna gain for a given physical antenna size. However, the present cellular networks must be upgraded due to the need for very concentrated transmissions. Care must be taken while building buildings and preserving connections when you transition to different transmission lines. The capacitive or inductive input impedance of the fringing fields across the transition zone generates distortion and subpar matching performance on the panel launch transmission line

feed. This article examines recent developments in the creation of a 64-element prototype mmW microstrip antenna array for massive MIMO applications. The suggested mmW microstrip antenna array system configuration is covered in detail. The adaptive algorithms that use least mean squares (LMS) and lowest mean square error are covered in this section. These techniques provide a significant improvement in the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) by introducing nulls in the interference direction. shows how printing a microstrip patch antenna on a low-temperature cofired ceramic (LTCC) substrate may be used to create a prototype mmW antenna array. offers a self-calibrating reference antenna for 64-element microstrip patch antennas and explains its experimental testing in mmW microstrip antenna arrays. The significant mutual coupling between the two antenna array halves of a MIMO system has been reduced using a number of techniques. In addition to cutting a slit into the ground, other traditional techniques for achieving minimal mutual coupling have been proposed, such as projecting a single or dual ground branch. Another unique neutralization technique that was just published links a neutralization line (NL) between the feeding strips or the shorting strips of antenna components. Reverse coupling may thus be turned on to reduce mutual coupling between antenna components that are close to one another. Therefore, a previously published antenna design for 4G applications (4G antenna module) is evaluated before being significantly updated in this study. The 4G antenna module is isolated with this antenna via NL and protruded ground approaches.

Some nations and areas have already established their own 5G wireless standards, which will be 100 times faster than the current fastest 4G LTE standard, in response to the need for data transfer speeds that go much beyond the 4G standard. The selection of the 3.5 GHz C band (3,400-3,600 MHz) for prospective broadband mobile services was one of the major achievements of world radio communication conference 2015 (WRC-15) in November 2015. As a result, mobile terminal devices that operate in this C band with huge MIMO antenna arrays are now a viable possibility for future 5G operation, in addition to taking into account the potential usage of beamforming methods that are predicted as enablers for 5G mobile systems. According to the author's understanding, the majority of internal two element MIMO antenna array mobile phone designs typically support LTE/wireless wide area network (WWAN) operation, which only takes into account 4G frequency ranges. The published research, however, recommends a hybrid dual-antenna that includes an open-slot and an inverted-F antenna and is only designed to function in the 3.6 GHz band. (3.4-3.8 GHz). The previously published antenna array has been expanded to include support for the WWAN/LTE operating frequencies in the 4G antenna module design that is shown here. It sports two 4G antennae, a sophisticated design, and perfect measurements. A bent shorting strip combined with a 6.8 nH chip inductor and a feeding strip supplied by a 50 micro coaxial feeding line make up each 4G antenna. Points A1 and A2 serve as the feeding points. (With point B1 and B2 functioning as shorting point).

As previously mentioned, the protruded ground plane will result in an increase in impedance matching in the lower bands, as well as decoupling effects in the higher bands, but it will also cause a drop in isolation in the lower bands. To enhance the benefits of decoupling in the lower bands, a neutralization line (NL) is loaded between the two 4G antenna components. Our 4G antenna module's findings are very consistent with those that have been made public. A combined dual resonance that may cover the lower bands for GSM 850/900 operations is possible as a consequence of the feeding strip and the shorting strip, which may both stimulate a fundamental resonant mode at 950 MHz and 850 MHz, respectively. The shorting strip can also produce a higher-order resonance around 1,800 MHz; this resonance, together with the protruded ground's resonance at about 2,600 MHz, may be able to enable GSM1800/1900/UMTS operations. This study has effectively described a multi-antenna module that combines 4G and 5G antenna modules and is appropriate for 4G/5G applications. These modules could provide coverage for the 4G antenna module's 824–960 MHz and 5G antenna module's 3,400–3,600 MHz bands, respectively, with their respective broad operational bands of 1,710–2,690 MHz and 824–960 MHz. A 5G antenna array's ergodic channel capacity, at around 40 bps/Hz with a 20-dB SNR, would be close to 7 times more in an 8 8 MIMO system than they would be in an ideal senior information security officer (SISO) system, according to calculations. S-parameters, radiation efficiency, antenna gain, radiation pattern, and ECCs are examples of common outcomes that might be used to create a MIMO system. Therefore, with the suggested multi-antenna module, future multi-mode smartphone applications are now feasible. Finally, the authors claim that there are no records of reports of combined 4G and 5G antenna modules in the public domain or anywhere else.

People are using the internet more often, and wireless communication technology is now advancing quickly. The creation of first-generation (1G), 2G, 3G, and most recently 4G LTE technologies. The scarcity of available frequency resources is one of the main problems that wireless communication is now confronting. Research on 5G wireless communication in the millimeter frequency band which spans from 20 to 300 GHz has begun in an effort to solve this issue. The frequency band between 24 and 60 GHz is most often utilized for 5G research. The IoT and 5G have already been used by a number of industries. Connecting millions of devices is one of the objectives of 5G technology. Future applications of 5G technology might include smart transportation, smart cities, and robots. Due to the ongoing reduction in size of mobile devices,

it is now possible to create tiny antennas that fit within them without compromising performance. As a result, microstrip patch antennas became more and more well-liked during the 20th century. A thin layer of metal foil is placed on top of a substrate for a microstrip patch antenna, and the substrate is grounded. It is simple to include this microstrip patch antenna onto the surface of this PCB. It may also be used in mobile devices. These antennas are often employed in the millimeter and microwave frequency bands.

The previous ten years have seen a substantial improvement in the condition of cellular communication networks, and market demand has been increasing. Mobile phone communication has to improve soon in terms of both execution and quality of service (QoS). Additionally, without antenna, it would be impossible to develop new wireless communication technologies. Complex antenna design configurations are required in this scenario due to new demands for the benefit of society. The advantages of microstriped patching antennas, such as their light weight, small size, cheap production cost, and capacity to double and treble frequency bandwidths, make them widely employed. High access is essential for the production of wireless application-specific directional microstrip antennas. A microstrip antenna's very tiny band width is its most crucial component. There are a number of solutions that have been developed to overcome these typical limitations, including limited impedance and axial ratio (AR), data transmission rate capacity, and restricted microstrip antenna bandwidth. Globally acknowledged analysts have created a wide range of forms and design frameworks. The expansion of consumers has caused a broad spectrum of social problems, according to a communication industry study. Future wireless communication technologies, including 5G and previous generations, are anticipated to utilize the millimeter to micrometer-range frequencies set down by the international teleconference union (ITU).

4. WIRELESS COMMUNICATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In a relatively short period of time, cellular mobile technology has advanced significantly from 0 G to 4G. In the first iteration of cellular technology, analogue speech was used. The following image provides a detailed overview of the recent rapid technological advancements brought on by 2G, 3G, and 4G technologies. Many generational approaches, including frequency reuse, line switching, circuit switching, packet switching modulation, and others, are employed to produce various generations of cellular mobile communications. We need high speed connection rates for the apps in order to make use of all of these capabilities. Mobile technology is a crucial aspect of everyday living in the contemporary world. In the old days, the main uses of mobile cellular technology were to make calls to subscribers or send texts, but today's usage of mobile devices has dramatically increased for a variety of purposes, such as navigation, online shopping, trading, booking tickets, services and home deliveries. As of now, practically all industrialized and emerging nations have successfully used 4G technology to meet the data transfer requirements required for app access. The 5G technology would be useful in overcoming the restrictions and limits in the features of great network coverage, black hole regions, connections, and spectrum crises in order to satisfy the needs of the present applications of free access to any requirement of the mobile subscribers. 5G technology would meet the primary demands of the current needs of mobile technology by delivering a more reliable connection, quicker data rates, and reduced latency. Furthermore, it provides more security. their research on 5G antennas was just published. For 5G, mmW frequencies are where the majority of microstrip antennas are employed. We created a 28 GHz inset fed elliptical micro strip patch antenna design for 5G technology using the HFSS program.

Mobile and portable gadgets have been incorporated into our everyday lives as a result of technical breakthroughs in communication and technology. As a consequence, the amount of data being sent through the Internet is growing. In order to provide these gadgets access to limitless, continuous, and content-rich services, the 5G of networks is being developed. The 5G network outperforms the 4G network in terms of data speed, QoS, and latency. Multiple wireless network generations are compared in the article. Additionally, some of the difficulties confronting the creation of 5G networks are examined, as well as some potential applications. Mobile devices all across the world are served by the cellular network. The academic community and the commercial sector are both working to provide better solutions for providing mobile devices with high-speed bandwidth and real-time services right now. The use of 5G might enable the next-generation wireless network to handle more end-to-end (E2E) connections as needed. In line with CISCO's analysis, mobile data traffic may rise from 1.5 ZB/year or 122 EB/month in 2017 to 4.8 Zettabytes (ZB) [1] yearly, or 396 exabytes (EB)/month, by 2022. A separate CISCO research [21]–[25] predicts that there will be 50 billion connected smart devices by the year 2020. Over the last ten years, ubiquitous computing has changed as a result of IoT's many applications in industries including smart cities, smart agriculture, and smart health. Numerous smart items and sensor nodes are part of the IoT concept. The sensor nodes track the predefined parameters and communicate online. By 2020, there will be billions of gadgets, with the typical individual having six to seven devices. There will be more than one trillion sensor nodes connected to the Internet by 2022. It is anticipated that over 45 trillion gadgets will be connected to the Internet during the

next 20 years. 4G must be replaced if services are to be continued for these mobile devices. Supposedly, a new generation of mobile phones is introduced every ten years.

The scope of 5G extends beyond radio technology to include cloud infrastructure, fixed host communication services, and other things. In addition to enhancing the ecosystem of the telecommunications network, the extension services of the 5G mobile network provide energy-efficient services for healthcare, agriculture, and smart city projects. By allowing everything from interpersonal communication to social networking, 5G lays the groundwork for digitalization. Due to digitalization, mobile communication has great potential, but it also faces significant obstacles. In 1981, the first generation (1G) of wireless networks was standardized for voice transmission. It is capable of handling data transfers at up to 2.4 Kbps. The total access communication system (TACS), the Nordic mobile phone system (AMPS), and others were the most widely used 1G-access technologies. Voice transmission in 1G was carried out via analogue transmissions. A couple of its flaws include poor signal quality, a small capacity, and irregular and less secure handoff.

In 1990, second-generation (2G) wireless networks were standardized. Data transmission rates of up to 64 Kbps were available, and it was mostly utilized for voice communication. Also possible is a sluggish two-way data flow. The three most widely used 2G access technologies are IS-95, code division multiple access (CDMA), and GSM. multimedia messaging services (MMS), text messages, and image messaging may all be sent using 2G technology. Additionally, it might provide secure point-to-point communication, enabling only the intended recipient to receive and read the message. Major problems with 2G's limitations were its poor data rate, constrained cell capacity, extended changeover periods, and restricted mobility. Additionally, 2G-capable phones have a constrained feature set. Second-generation wireless systems were being developed at the time. general packet radio services (GPRS) are the packet-based switching method that is suggested. In addition to the services offered by 2G, improved communication may also be given via the use of packet switching and circuit switching methods. It is capable of handling data transfers at up to 144 Kbps. The three 2.5 G-access technologies that were most widely used were GPRS, CDMA2000, and enhanced data for global evolution (EDGE) for GSM. Wireless networks of the third generation (3G) were standardized in 2000. The primary goals of 2G's design were voice communication and 2 Mbps-capable high-speed data transmissions. universal mobile telecommunications systems (UMTS), wideband code division multiple access (WCDMA), and CDMA2000 were the most widely used 3G access methods. To make the most of 3G smartphone capabilities, specialized software for video chatting, online gaming, email, social networking sites like Facebook and Orkut. was created. It was a 3G wireless network advancement that became standardized in 2008. It was mainly created to increase the data capacity of the current 3G networks, and it is capable of 3.6 Mbps data transmission rates. High speed downlink packet access (HSDPA) and high-speed uplink packet access (HSUPA) were the two most used 3G access technologies. It is possible that the 3.75 G network will replace the 3G network. Technology known as high-speed packet access plus (HSPA+) was used. It used Fixed worldwide interoperability for microwave access (WiMAX) and LTE technology. These technologies enable several users to access high-speed services concurrently, including on-demand movies, composite web services and social networking services. Even if 3G technology revolutionizes communication, there are limitations including high installation costs, incompatibility with 2G systems, and the risks of harmful magnetic wave radiation to our brains. 2010 saw the standardization of 4G wireless networks. With QoS, 4G can handle data transmission rates of up to 300 Mbps. Users are able to watch high definition (HD) movies and play online games through 4G. Voice over LTE (VoLTE) networks are the most widely used 4G access method. For voice, utilize IP packets. LTE is currently being standardized by the 3GPP.

It offers safe mobility and cuts down on latency for crucial applications. IoT-enabled gadgets may now efficiently interact with one another thanks to it as well. The cost of installing and buying gear for 4G is greater than it was for 3G. High-end, multipurpose devices compatible with 4G technology are necessary for communication. Instead of efficient delivery, the fundamental goal of 3G and 4G networks is content distribution to mobile devices. There is essentially no delay when using the 5G wireless network to connect billions of devices. 2020 is the planned year for 5G standardization. With QoS, 5G is capable of 10Gbps data transmission rates. Faster speeds make it feasible to play online games and view ultra-high definition (UHD) videos. 5G networks aim to provide very low latency, excellent dependability, and security in addition to high-speed mobile internet and higher throughput in contrast to 3G or 4G networks. Complexity exists in the 5G infrastructure. Installation of a significant number of base stations (BS) is necessary within a constrained geographic area. It will increase network costs while enhancing data transmission speeds and reducing energy use. In order to achieve high-speed, massive multiple input and multiple output (mMIMO) and cognitive radio networks (CRN) designs will be used. mMIMO employs more antennas than communication devices in order to maximize efficiency. A wavelength of 1-10 mm and a frequency range of 30-300 GHz are used in mMIMO. There are two distinct channels one for uploading and one for downloading in the 4G network since half-duplex communication is used. Access and backhaul will use the same channel, however,

since 5G is intended for full duplex transmission. It will boost connection capacity, conserve the frequency spectrum, and be more cost-effective despite the fact that interference makes it exceedingly challenging to implement. Thus, a technique to decrease the effects of interference is also necessary. Analogue voice was the only kind of speech that early communication systems could accept, but contemporary systems provide a broad variety of applications to a huge user base. Only voice could be supported on the first mobile systems. Mobile telecommunications have recently continued to grow thanks to the creation of wireless networks that operate in the 2G, 3G, and 4G bands, respectively. This change has led to the emergence of new digital networking methods, including as modulation, frequency reuse, packet switching, and physical layer emulation, among others. New multimedia applications for mobile users are becoming more prevalent because to the growing usage of smart devices and IP-based networks nowadays. Due to the oversupply of these programs on the open market, mobile device users and service providers now have more alternatives. Future mobile communications will probably look quite different from what they do today. However, as the world around us becomes more networked, we are already beginning to observe the growing influence of human capabilities. While UHD video and bigger displays will be the key drivers of rising demand for portable internet in the future.

Users will undoubtedly see constant Gbps internet speeds on the next 5G network across a variety of user situations. Simply defined, 5G is a brand-new radio technology for wireless connectivity. It opens the door to new applications and communication channels, many of which we have only just started to investigate. Due to worries about capacity, mmW mobile communications techniques as well as a micro-strip receiver have both been developed for the 5G cellular network/device. Its main goal is to successfully integrate wireless and cellular networks like WLAN, Bluetooth, GSM, and 3G while protecting the spectrum for 4G and 5G networks. Small size, light weight, cheap cost, and suitability for planer and nonlinear surfaces are the defining characteristics of micro-strip patch receivers (MPAs). MPAs are both appealing and useful because of these qualities. They may only be usable in a few systems, however, because to their very constricted bandwidth. Since traditional electronics are no longer as economically viable for producing high-frequency mm-wave electric signals, there is a rising need for mm-wave alerts to be generated simultaneously in the optical domain. Therefore, the photonic technology that has been previously presented and demonstrated as well as the variation and circulation of 60 GHz thickness band transmissions are shown in these paintings. A totally photonics-based mm-wave is essentially a laser beam coupled with two or more coherent longitudinal modes with a frequency spacing equal to the necessary mmW. The accurate electrical mmW may be obtained by beating the longitudinal technique with each alteration in the photodiode.

5. CONCLUSION

The main goal of this study is to examine a microstrip patch antenna for mmW mobile communication at 38 GHz frequency utilizing the basic microstrip conductor technology and line calculation analysis using HFSS computer code. Another crucial factor to take into account is the information coverage range of an antenna. Typically, just data on resistance or come losses is offered. It is essential to realize that information measure may be defined in a variety of ways, including polarization information measure, potency bandwidth, and radial asymmetry bandwidth. To give information metrics, radial asymmetry and potency are often coupled. It was suggested that a multi-band microstrip antenna be included into the smartphone in order to support its essential wireless functions, such as 3G, 4G, Bluetooth, and the upcoming 5G mobile telecommunications systems. The design of a tiny antenna is crucial since customers are always asking for products that are more compact, thinner, and faster than before. The features of the substrate may allow the suggested antenna to fit the applications while remaining small and compact. The results of comparisons between data from models and testing highlighted the high degree of agreement between the data and the advised antenna.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Gao, Q. Luo, and F. Zhu, *Circularly polarized antennas*. USA: Wiley-IEEE Press, 2013.
- [2] W. Liang, Y.-C. Jiao, Y. Luan, and C. Tian, "A dual-band circularly polarized complementary antenna," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 14, pp. 1153–1156, 2015, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2015.2392787.
- [3] J.-H. Lu and C.-W. Liou, "Planar dual-band circular polarization monopole antenna for wireless local area networks," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 14, pp. 478–481, 2015, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2014.2368137.
- [4] T. Kumar and A. R. Harish, "Broadband circularly polarized printed slot-monopole antenna," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 12, pp. 1531–1534, 2013, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2013.2291436.
- [5] A. Birwal, S. Singh, B. K. Kanaujia, and S. Kumar, "Broadband CPW-fed circularly polarized antenna for IoT-based navigation system," *International Journal of Microwave and Wireless Technologies*, vol. 11, no. 08, pp. 835–843, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1017/S1759078719000461.
- [6] N. Ravikumar, N. H. Metcalfe, J. Ravikumar, and R. Prasad, "Smartphone applications for providing ubiquitous healthcare over cloud with the advent of embeddable implants," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 86, no. 3, pp. 1439–1446, Feb. 2016,

- doi: 10.1007/s11277-015-2999-5.
- [7] Y. Li, C. Wang, H. Yuan, N. Liu, H. Zhao, and X. Li, "A 5G MIMO antenna manufactured by 3-D printing method," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 16, pp. 657–660, 2017, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2016.2596297.
 - [8] D. Wu, S. W. Cheung, T. I. Yuk, and X. L. Sun, "A planar MIMO antenna for mobile phones," in *Progress in Electromagnetics Research Symposium (PIERS 2013)*, 2013, pp. 1150–1152.
 - [9] A. S. Bhadouria and M. Kumar, "Microstrip patch antenna for radiolocation using DGS with improved gain and bandwidth," in *2014 International Conference on Advances in Engineering & Technology Research (ICAETR - 2014)*, Aug. 2014, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ICAETR.2014.7012873.
 - [10] M. K. Khandelwal, B. K. Kanaujia, and S. Kumar, "Defected ground structure: fundamentals, analysis, and applications in modern wireless trends," *International Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 2017, pp. 1–22, 2017, doi: 10.1155/2017/2018527.
 - [11] B. Gary, "An introduction to defected ground structures in microstrip circuits," *High Frequency Electronics*, vol. 7, no. 11, pp. 50–54, 2008.
 - [12] A. K. Verma and A. Kumar, "Synthesis of microstrip lowpass filter using defected ground structures," *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 5, no. 12, 2011, doi: 10.1049/iet-map.2011.0071.
 - [13] K.-L. Wong, *Compact and broadband microstrip antennas*. John Wiley & Sons, 2002.
 - [14] R. Xu, J.-Y. Li, J.-J. Yang, K. Wei, and Y.-X. Qi, "A design of u-shaped slot antenna with broadband dual circularly polarized radiation," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 65, no. 6, pp. 3217–3220, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2017.2689069.
 - [15] A. A. Deshmukh, A. A. Desai, P. Kadam, and K. P. Ray, "Ultra-wide band E-shaped patch antenna," in *2016 IEEE Annual India Conference (INDICON)*, Dec. 2016, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/INDICON.2016.7839154.
 - [16] G. Z. Rafi and L. Shafai, "Wideband V-slotted diamond-shaped microstrip patch antenna," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 40, no. 19, 2004, doi: 10.1049/el:20046186.
 - [17] P. N. Shinde and J. P. Shinde, "Design of compact pentagonal slot antenna with bandwidth enhancement for multiband wireless applications," *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 69, no. 10, pp. 1489–1494, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.aeue.2015.07.001.
 - [18] S. D. Targonski, R. B. Waterhouse, and D. M. Pozar, "Wideband aperture coupled stacked patch antenna using thick substrates," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 32, no. 21, 1996, doi: 10.1049/el:19961306.
 - [19] J.-W. Wu, J.-Y. Ke, C. F. Jou, and C.-J. Wang, "Microstrip-fed broadband circularly polarised monopole antenna," *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 4, no. 4, 2010, doi: 10.1049/iet-map.2008.0400.
 - [20] C. Deng, Y. Li, Z. Zhang, and Z. Feng, "A wideband sequential-phase fed circularly polarized patch array," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 62, no. 7, pp. 3890–3893, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2014.2321380.
 - [21] X. Fang, G. Wen, D. Inserra, Y. Huang, and J. Li, "Compact wideband CPW-fed meandered-slot antenna with slotted Y-shaped central element for Wi-Fi, WiMAX, and 5G applications," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 66, no. 12, pp. 7395–7399, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2018.2869254.
 - [22] B. Y. M. Sadiq and A. Maher, "Design and simulation of meander line antenna for LTE communications based on defected ground structure," *Ciência e Técnica Vitivinícola*, vol. 30, no. 11, pp. 15–29, 2015.
 - [23] Y. Hong and J. Choi, "60 GHz patch antenna array with parasitic elements for smart glasses," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 1252–1256, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2018.2841512.
 - [24] J.-N. Hwang and F.-C. Chen, "Reduction of the peak SAR in the human head with metamaterials," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 54, no. 12, pp. 3763–3770, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2006.886501.
 - [25] Kaburcuk Fatih and Elsherbeni Atef Z, "Temperature rise and SAR distribution at wide range of frequencies in a human head due to an antenna radiation," *The Applied Computational Electromagnetics Society Journal (ACES)*, pp. 367–372, 2018.

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